

USE OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION LESSONS AND THEIR SIGNIFICANCE IN INCREASE OF LESSON EFFICIENCY

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ABSTRACT: In the current era, it is the demand of the time for teachers to have high professional training, pedagogical skills, high spiritual and moral qualities, deep knowledge of ideology, effective use of modern pedagogical technologies and interactive methods in educational work. This article provides information on the use of new modern pedagogical technologies in the organization of physical education classes in higher educational institutions and their importance in increasing the effectiveness of the lesson.

KEY WORDS: Innovation, Perfect System, Cluster, Diagnostic, Dissemination, Individual, Process.

The purpose of teaching features in the course of physical education and sports training is to teach pupils and students the requirements for physical development of the body and a healthy lifestyle. At the same time, physical training, sports and wellness events will greatly help to master professional training.

In the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, based on the above analysis, it is planned to carry out the following measures to actively involve the recruiters in the process of training highly qualified teachers:

- based on the uniqueness of educational areas and specialties, form the content of curricula and programs and the distribution of hours in specialized subjects based on the latest achievements of science and technology in cooperation with personnel customers;
- formation of the topics of graduation-qualification works, master's and doctoral theses based on the real sector of the economy, as well as territorial (province, district, city, neighborhood, territorial object) problems and transition to in-depth research of the topics in a narrow scope;
- to strengthen the relations of higher educational institutions and production enterprises and organize their operation in a cluster method;

A perfect system of innovative technology has not been developed in higher educational institutions. At the same time, the necessity of this system is the need of the times, because innovative technology is a process that increases the efficiency of mastering students' knowledge, skills and qualifications based on a certain system. It should be reflected in the tasks, content, methods, means, forms of organization and results of studying through innovative technologies. It is widely understood that innovative methods are not only a system of students' knowledge, but also a didactic condition that ensures the development of their perceptive abilities, activities, interests, mental activities.

Sport, which is a component of physical education and all its aspects, educates the desire for victory, achieving high results, helps to mobilize the physical, mental and moral qualities of a person, prolongs the creative life of citizens and strengthens their health, all this

is especially important in the context of increased competition. is important. The involvement of the mass of the population in physical education and sports, as well as success in international sports competitions, testify to the viability and spiritual strength of any country. After implementing the model of organizational-methodological provision of the process of developing and improving the professional competence of the physical education teacher in qualification training and providing this process with specific pedagogical technologies, determining the level of development of physical education teachers in the public education system and there was a need for diagnosis.

The system of training of physical education teachers should be aimed at solving the following tasks:

- creating conditions for free, multi-vector, personal and professional growth of the teacher;
- that the general meaningful vector of qualification improvement is focused primarily on the main examined directions of modernization of education;
- actualization and multifaceted dissemination of teachers' experience (including advanced training);
- creating conditions for the teacher to constantly and objectively assess his/her own qualifications;
- implementation of interactivity, modularity, design, remoteness and continuity as factors of ensuring a creative, individual approach to professional development.

The teacher turns to the achievements of pedagogy, psychology and educational methodology in search of ways to acquire advanced methods and apply them in his work. A creative pedagogue compares the experience of others with his own without analyzing it directly, and then accepts its advanced aspects. Speaking about the unique characteristics of the teaching profession, it is necessary to reiterate that its essence is mainly knowledge, vocational training, and accordingly, it is necessary for him to study all the time. This characteristic of the teacher's profession requires him to constantly work on himself, to acquire independent knowledge. The key to success in his work is continuous work on himself. The ability of a physical education teacher to creatively learn from his colleagues and advanced foreign experiences, to apply them in his practice, and to continuously improve his knowledge, skills and qualifications through independent reading of textbooks and methodical magazines and literature, has a positive effect on the educational process. shows.

Pupils and students' physical education activities are in the form of morning physical education, physical education classes, sports club training, sports fitness competitions and holidays. Morning physical education classes are held in public in student dormitories and independently in residence halls and families. The scientific work is one of the first to be done today. It analyzes the importance of physical training and sports and health activities of pupils and students in raising the young generation as a well-rounded person. Forms of improvement of this process are studied.

Physical education of pupils and students is an organized pedagogical process of their physical activities. Physical education activities in an educational institution differ in very diverse forms that require enthusiasm, initiative, and organization from pupils and students. They help to educate pupils and students in organizational skills, activity and resourcefulness.

The purpose of physical education of students in an educational institution:

1. Health.

2. Educate to become a mature person in every way.
3. Preparing for the defense of the Motherland and the cocktail.

Based on the purpose of physical education, the main tasks of physical education are defined in terms of health, exercise, physical development, and formation of movement skills and abilities of pupils and students:

the criteria and foundation of its activity are hidden. It is necessary to develop the spiritual qualities of the participants and connect them with life, society, and the needs of the work. It is necessary to encourage the participants in the process of physical education to actively participate in the struggle to build a new society. How they live, what they think about, how they work in production, how they study at school, how they behave in the family, in public places, in order to educate employees in the spirit of the idea of national independence. Physical education specialists should know how to spend their time and others. It is necessary for physical education specialists to know the level of development of physical abilities of the participants, to study individual character traits, moral qualities of intellect, perception, emotional will, and individual differences in static needs. In the process of independent training, pupils' and students' attitude to physical education and sports is formed, the skills of independent exercise, movement and sports are increased. Along with teaching vital movements in independent training, physical qualities such as strength, endurance, flexibility, quickness, and agility are improved. Changes occur in the body as a result of the development of each physical quality. The organs of the human body are strengthened and the blood circulation develops as a result of improvement.

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